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Selection of feasibility studies for linking HBM and health studies, and linking to administrative data sources

Additional Deliverable Report

AD 11.3

WP 11 - Linking HBM, health studies and registers

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2 Summary

In both human biomonitoring (HBM) and health studies, data is collected through fieldwork with similar infrastructures. Therefore, combination of these two study types would be theoretically possible and provide added value through increased information collected on chemical exposures, health outcomes, and lifestyles. Until now, limited number of health measures has been included in many HBM studies but HBM modules are lacking from most health studies. More information about opportunities and obstacles on linking HBM and health studies is needed. Three proposed feasibility studies (Finland, Germany and UK/England) have been selected. They will be conducted to learn more about opportunities and obstacles in different settings.

Administrative registers such as hospitalization and mortality registers could be used to obtain information on disease history prior to baseline examination as well as morbidity and mortality follow-up for HBM and health study cohorts. This type of register linkage is commonly conducted in Nordic countries in which personal identification codes are systematically used in all registers as well as in available sampling frames. To learn more about details how such register linkage between survey (HBM or health study) data and administrative registers could be done and what are the prerequisites for that, nine theoretical case studies from six countries (Austria, the Czech Republic, Denmark, Finland, Norway and Sweden) will be conducted. These theoretical case studies will provide detailed descriptions of the process required together with usual timelines, required documents and estimated costs to do the record linkage in these countries.

Register linkage can provide

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3 Introduction

The European Human Biomonitoring Initiative (HBM4EU) is a joint effort of 28 countries (24 European Member States, three associated countries and Switzerland), the European Environment Agency and the European Commission, co-funded under Horizon 2020.

The main objective of HBM4EU is to use human biomonitoring (HBM) to assess human exposure to chemicals in Europe in order to better understand the associated health impacts and to improve chemical risk assessment. HBM4EU will generate knowledge on chemical exposure levels in the population and their health effects.

In parallel to HBM studies, national health examination surveys (HESs), dietary surveys and disease specific health surveys are conducted in many European countries. HESs are surveys where information collected by questionnaire(s) is complemented with information obtained by physical measurements such as blood pressure and anthropometric measurements, and by analysis of biomarkers from biological samples. The European Health Examination Survey (EHES)¹ was established in 2010 to coordinate the development of national HESs in Europe. Between 2000 and 2017, 15 European countries² have conducted a national HES and in many countries smaller, regional or disease specific surveys or dietary surveys have been carried out.

Since for both HBM studies and HESs, data is collected through fieldwork, which is one of the largest expenses for such studies and for which the needed infrastructures are very similar, the potential to combine these two types of studies has been considered. This could result in more cost-effective ways to conduct health and human biomonitoring, and in providing data to study exposure-health outcome relationships.

Human biomonitoring and health studies have many similarities in terms of infrastructure and procedures required for their implementation. However, in practice, the opportunity to add a HBM module to an ongoing/planned health study (and vice versa) is rarely used. Some reasons for this were obtained through questionnaire survey organized by WP11 in 2017 and results were reported in HBM4EU deliverable D11.1 'Report on opportunities and obstacles of combining HBM and health studies, availability of health studies with biological samples, availability of administrative registers, and guidelines for combining HBM and health studies'³.

HBM and health studies can in some countries also be linked to administrative registers. WP11 also conducted a questionnaire survey in 2017 about availability of administrative registers and possibilities to link them to survey data. Results from this survey were also reported in HBM4EU deliverable D11.1.

Case studies are needed to further investigate the opportunities and obstacles related to 1) combining HBM and health studies and 2) linking HBM/health studies to administrative registers. For this purpose, three case studies on the feasibility of combining HBM and health studies were selected after an Internal Call and will be conducted in 2019-2020 (see Section 4). Nine examples of record linkage studies have been selected and will be conducted at first in a theoretical setting (see Section 5).

¹ <http://www.ehes.info>

² http://www.ehes.info/national/national_hes_status.htm

³ Deliverable D11.1 available at <https://www.hbm4eu.eu/upload-work-package/get/file/Deliverable-11.1-Report-on-opportunities-and-obstacles-of-combining-HBM-and-health-studies-availability-of-health-studies-with-biological-samples-availability-of-administrative-registers-and-guidelines-for-combining-HBM-and-health-studies.pdf>

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4 Feasibility studies on linking HBM and health studies

4.1 Aim of the feasibility studies

Under Task 11.1, a questionnaire survey about the opportunities and obstacles on combining HBM and health studies was prepared in 2017 and distributed mainly to principle investigators (PI) of health and dietary studies. This survey aimed to identify opportunities but also possible problems related to the combination of HBM and health studies in theory since only few countries, mainly Germany and France, have done that on a national scale previously. Results from this survey were published in the D11.1 'Report on opportunities and obstacles of combining HBM and health studies, availability of health studies with biological samples, availability of administrative registers, and guidelines for combining HBM and health studies'⁴.

Results of the survey showed that most of the health surveys (93%) collect and store biological samples, which in theory could also be used for HBM analyses. Also in several surveys (68%) these types of analyses have already been done. Most often reported reasons for not including chemical measurements to health surveys were:

- not considered relevant for the aim of the study;
- lack of funding for additional sample collection for measurements of chemicals;
- lack of funding for laboratory analysis;
- collection of additional samples was not seen logistically practical;
- lack of storage space for additional samples; and
- lack of knowledge and capacities related to sample handling and laboratory analysis.

Since only Germany and France have experience on linking HBM and health studies at the national level, it was evaluated that experiences from other countries and settings as well are needed. Feasibility studies are designed to provide better understanding on crucial steps in combining HBM and health studies, the need for possible compromises in the contents of the two study types, the added value of combining HBM and health studies, and issues where possible problems are experienced.

4.2 Selection of the feasibility studies

4.2.1 Selection process

Additional feasibility studies were selected through the Internal Call (IC) process of the HBM4EU. Topics for the first Internal Calls were selected in June 2017 and approved by the Governing Board in September 2017. Thereafter, the final call text for the IC of the additional feasibility studies was prepared by the leader of WP11 (THL) in collaboration with WP3 Internal Calls. Other Task 11.4 (Feasibility studies) partners were not involved in the preparation of the call text to ensure that they do not have a conflict of interest, and thereby would be not eligible to apply if interested.

The call text for the additional feasibility studies was based on the Additional Deliverable 11.2 Criteria for feasibility studies⁵.

⁴ Deliverable D11.1 available at <https://www.hbm4eu.eu/upload-work-package/get/file/Deliverable-11.1-Report-on-opportunities-and-obstacles-of-combining-HBM-and-health-studies-availability-of-health-studies-with-biological-samples-availability-of-administrative-registers-and-guidelines-for-combining-HBM-and-health-studies.pdf>

⁵ Additional Deliverable 11.2 available at <https://www.hbm4eu.eu/upload-work-package/get/file/Additional-Deliverable-11.2-Criteria-for-feasibility-studies.pdf>

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This document provided the framework for the feasibility studies. The actual call text was published in the HBM4EU internal web site and call documents were at the INSERM site at <https://sp2013.inserm.fr/sites/eva/appels-a-projets/Pages/HBM4EU-WP3-%E2%80%93-Call-1-2018-.aspx>.

The funding provided through IC process for the additional feasibility studies did not cover analysis of the biological samples for HBM biomarkers.

WP3 Internal Calls was responsible for the technical execution of the IC, i.e. preparation of the proposal template, guidelines and electronic platform, and organizing the review of the proposals and consultation with the HBM4EU Scientific Advisory Board (SAB) about the outcomes of the evaluation.

Each proposal was evaluated by three independent reviewers. Each reviewer evaluated all proposals for one call. Evaluation included three components:

1. **Excellence.**

- a. The extent to which the project addressed the objectives of the 'call for projects'.
- b. The clarity and originality of the objectives beyond the current state-of-the art.
- c. The novelty of the approach.

2. **Impact.**

- a. Did the proposal contribute to unlock scientific bottlenecks?
- b. Did the proposal open new scientific and technical perspectives?
- c. Will the proposal have an effect towards the scientific community and policy makers?

3. **Quality and efficiency of implementation.**

- a. The scientific excellence of the coordinator attested by the publications, the patents, and his/her aptitude to be a group leader able to manage the project.
- b. The extent to which the participants collectively constitute a consortium of high quality and consider whether their complementary competences allow them to carry their tasks.
- c. Is the budget requested in balance with the project objectives?
- d. Will the proposed methodology be able to fulfil the objectives of the project in a competitive manner?
- e. Is the proposed work feasible within the project duration?
- f. The appropriateness of the allocation and integration of the work proposed by each participant.
- g. The matching of the timetable and the methodology with the objectives of the project.

The process with timeline has been illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Process and timeline for the Internal Call

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4.2.2 Selected studies

By the deadline, three proposals were received. External reviewers and the SAB recommended funding two of them. The Management Board (MB) made their decision on the outcomes of the Internal Call during their June 2018 meeting based on the external reviews, SAB recommendations and detailed discussions, and recommended two studies for funding; one from Germany and one from UK/England. Since Finland (THL) had a conflict of interest as the leader of the WP11 and therefore could not apply for IC, it was agreed already in the June 2017 MB meeting that Finland may conduct a feasibility study without participating in the IC. Thus, the following three feasibility studies will be conducted, assuming that the Governing Board will approve them in their September 2018 meeting as part of Annual Work Programme 2019.

1. In Leipzig, Germany, the LIFE-Adult study cohort was established in 2011-2014. For the cohort, 10,000 randomly selected individuals aged 40-79 years were selected together with a subset of 400 participants aged 18-39 years. The study includes a very extensive list of objective health measurements and biobanked biological samples. The planned feasibility study will test how a HBM module could be incorporated into the follow-up study of the original LIFE-Adult cohort to be conducted in 2018-2019. The plan is to recruit 400 participants mainly aged 60+ years, for the feasibility study during 2019. Blood samples, urine, saliva, oral biofilm, nasal secretion and hair will be collected from the participants during the follow-up study and relevant HBM questionnaire modules will be included in the LIFE-Adult questionnaire.

Involved partners in Germany are the Fraunhofer Institute for Biomedical Engineering (IBMT) and Leipzig Research Centre for Civilization Diseases (LIFE).

2. UK/England has a national health examination survey (HES), Health Survey for England (HSE), which is conducted annually among residents of England without age limit. In HSE all interviews and physical examinations, including collection of biological samples, are conducted at the participants' home. The planned feasibility study will test how a HBM module can be incorporated into HSE. The feasibility study is planned to cover adolescents (16-19 years) and adults (20-49 years). The plan is to recruit 150 adolescent and 150 adult participants, to collect spot urine and blood samples from them, and to include relevant HBM questionnaire modules to a survey questionnaire.

Involved partners in UK/England are Department of Health (DH-PHE), Institute of Occupational Medicine (IOM), Natural Environment Research Council (NERC-BGS) and Health and Safety Laboratory (HSL).

3. In Finland, children go through regular health check-ups several times during their first year of life and thereafter annually until they are 16. Most of these health check-ups are conducted by a nurse but at age 4 months, 18 months, 4 years, 6-8 years, 10-12 years, and 12-15 years, they are more extensive medical examinations conducted by a doctor and a nurse. On starting school (7+ years), children are transferred over to the school health care system. Regular health check-ups have nearly 100% coverage. This feasibility study will test how a HBM module could be incorporated into these regular health check-ups. The feasibility study is planned to take place in Kuopio region and include 5th and 6th graders (aged 10-12 years) from selected schools. The plan is to recruit 300 children and collect at least spot urine.

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The possibility to collect also blood samples depends on the level of collaboration with school nurses and doctors and availability of staff resources at the school health care system, as well as the ethical approval of the study, and parents' and children's willingness to give consent, which all are difficult to estimate before the pilot study. Relevant HBM questionnaire modules will be included in the study.

Involved partner in Finland is the National Institute for Health and Welfare (THL).

Ideally, the feasibility studies should have wide representation of Europe but due to limited number of applications to the Internal Call this was not possible. Small number of applications also prevented better support for the overall sampling strategy to obtain European representative data from aligned studies planned under Task 8.1. On the other hand, under Task 8.1, there are few national health examination surveys from which biobanked samples will be used for aligned studies. This can provide some additional information also for feasibility study.

The study groups of the selected feasibility studies will prepare a more detailed study plan (Milestone MS21, due M36). In each study plan, selected studies will ensure the use of HBM4EU standardized protocols and questionnaires to extend feasible. It may be that due to already existing protocols on selected studies require some compromises to both directions but this is obviously part of the feasibility study. Each study aims to include at least substance specific questionnaires for the 1st priority substances relevant for their covered age group. Since questionnaires for the 2nd priority substances are not yet available (due towards the end of December 2018), and studies have to proceed with their ethical approval process, it may be that questionnaires for the 2nd priority chemicals cannot be included to them.

Since the funding for IC did not cover analysis of biological samples for HBM biomarkers, it is still open what actually can be analysed at the end. This issue has to be further discussed within the Management Board and with WP9 in the framework of available funding taking into account also 50% own contribution required from the countries. All selected studies have stated that they have interest to analyse at least the 1st priority substances and possibly also the 2nd priority substances on the collected samples if there is funding for this.

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5 Theoretical studies on linking HBM/health studies to administrative registers

5.1 Aim of the theoretical studies

Record linkage is a cost-effective way to obtain information on disease history concerning the time before the baseline examination as well as follow-up information on individuals of a study cohort. Under Task 11.5, a questionnaire survey about the availability of administrative registers and possibility to link survey data to the register data was prepared and distributed in 2017 through national hub contact points for register owners or researchers working with these registers. Results from this survey were published in the D11.1 ‘Report on opportunities and obstacles of combining HBM and health studies, availability of health studies with biological samples, availability of administrative registers, and guidelines for combining HBM and health studies’⁶.

Results of the survey showed that all countries that replied to the survey had at least one administrative register. Because it was evident, that all registers were not reported in the survey, further inquiries have been conducted in 2018 to close these gaps. The most commonly reported problems related to linking of survey data to administrative registers were related to lack of common personal identification between different data sets within a country.

Record linkage is common in the Nordic countries, which have unique personal identification number and this number is systematically used in all registers as well as survey sampling frames. In other countries, record linkage is not conducted as commonly or routine systems that would enable the linkage may be missing. Therefore, it would be helpful to have a few detailed, step-by-step examples on how record linkage is carried out in practise and what are the required legal processes behind it. All this resulted to the decision within Task 11.5 to prepare a set of theoretical studies on record linkage. These studies are purely describing the process and will not include any new analysis at this point.

The aim of these theoretical studies is to provide detailed information about how record linkage can/could be conducted in different countries involved as partners of Task 11.5. More specifically, the aim is to gather information, among others, on what the requirements for such record linkage are (data protection, ethics, technical and practical procedures etc.) and what kind of register data could be obtained. In future, these theoretical studies may result in real record linkage studies, if seen feasible in relation to study questions and available funding.

The proposed content for these theoretical studies is following:

1. Description of the selected HBM or health study/cohort
 - A short description of selected study/cohort including
 - Description of target population
 - Sample selection
 - Aims of the study
2. Ethical approval and data protection
 - What does the existing ethical and data protection approval cover?
 - Does it cover record linkage?
 - If yes, which registers?
 - Is there a time limit for how many years ahead the approval is applicable?
 - If it doesn't cover record linkage?

⁶ Deliverable D11.1 available at <https://www.hbm4eu.eu/deliverables/>

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- What would be required to obtain permission to do the record linkage?
 - Do you require some other permission such as permission from register owner to do the record linkage?
 - If yes, what kind of permission(s) is/are required?
3. Administrative registers
- What are the relevant administrative registers for the study plan?
 - A short description of these registers, including
 - Who is the register owner?
 - When was the register established?
 - What kind of information is included in the register?
 - What is the coverage of the register (based on published literature or other material)?
4. Record linkage
- Description of record linkage in practice
 - Who performs the record linkage, i.e. how goes the process?
 - What are the identifiers used for record linkage?
 - Are there costs related to record linkage?
 - How long does it usually take to obtain linked data?
 - After the record linkage has been done, can research group get data with or without identifiers (identified, pseudonymised, or anonymised), i.e. is it possible to add other register data?
 - Has the new EU General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) changed the procedures of record linkage in your country?
5. Outcome of the record linkage study
- Did you obtain/would you obtain information on disease history (which diseases) prior to baseline examination?
 - Did you obtain/would you obtain follow-up information? On which outcomes?
 - Did you obtain supporting SES information from register?
6. Possible limitations/problems encountered/expected

5.2 Selection of the theoretical studies

Each country involved in the Task 11.5, i.e. Austria, the Czech Republic, Denmark, Finland, Norway and Sweden, selected at least one HBM or health study from their country which, at least in theory, could be linked to health related administrative registers. Administrative registers of interest are: causes of death, cancer register(s), patient register, prescription of medications register and birth register.

The following studies were selected.

Austria

Austria selected two studies. The first study includes 114 students from the Medical University of Vienna. They were examined in 2001-2003 and their mean age was 25 years. The sample was a convenience sample of the students.⁷ The second study includes 53 women aged 50+ years from

⁷ Hutter HP, Wallner P, Moshammer H, Hartl W, Sattelberger R, Lorbeer G, Kundi M. Synthetic musks in blood of healthy young adults: relationship to cosmetics use. *Sci Total Environ.* 2009 407(17):4821-5. doi: 10.1016/j.scitotenv.2009.05.026.

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Vienna. They were examined in 2004-2005 and their mean age was 59 years. Sample was a convenience sample of patients at an angiology ambulatory clinic in Hanusch Hospital in Vienna.⁸

Czech Republic

Czech Republic selected two studies, both of which are coordinated by the Masaryk University in Brno, the Czech Republic. The first one is the CELSPAC.TNG cohort, where recruitment and sample collection was initiated in 2015 and is on-going. Available are cord blood, meconium, mothers' blood and urine. Accredited laboratories of RECETOX RI are capable of analysis of organic (PCBs, OCPs, CUPs, BFRs, OPFRs, PFCs, PAHs, phthalates, bisphenols) as well as toxic metals, and develop also new approaches for targeted screening and non-target analysis.

The second study is the ELSPAC cohort, which is a birth cohort recruited in 1991-1992 (96% of children born in Brno) and followed for 20 years. The cohort will be re-assessed in 2018. Blood and urine will be collected and analysed by the accredited laboratories of RECETOX RI (see above).

Denmark

Denmark selected two studies. The first study is the Odense Child Cohort which includes 2500 mother-child pairs. Women living in the municipality of Odense who were pregnant between 2010 and 2012 were invited to participate. At the time of inclusion, a blood sample was drawn and the participants filled out a questionnaire on general health, lifestyle and social factors. A urine sample was collected at week 28 and PFAS, phthalates and BPA were measured for 650-870 women. Questionnaires focusing on the child's health and well-being were completed at age 3 months, 18 months, 3 years, 5 years and 7 years. Together with the birth records, these were the sources of data. In addition, in 2014, 1647 children from the original cohort were invited to participate in a study of childhood infections in which symptoms of infection had to be reported by text messages every second week (26 times) during one year.

The second study is the Inter99 Study which includes a random sample of 6,784 individuals aged 30-60 years from the general Danish population investigated in 1999-2001. Metabolic markers incl. lipid profile and glucose tolerance test were obtained, and the participants were followed repeatedly with both clinical examinations and through registries. 4,330 individuals participated at the 5-year follow-up.

Finland

From Finland, the DILCOM 2007 study was selected. The DILCOM study was a sub-study of the national FINRISK 2007 health examination survey. The main focus of the DILCOM study was on dietary, lifestyle and genetic determinants of obesity and metabolic syndrome. All 6,258 participants, men and women aged 25-74 years, of the main FINRISK survey were invited a couple of months later to a more detailed examination of obesity and metabolic syndrome. The survey included questionnaires, objective health measurements and collection of biological samples. For a sub-sample of participants (1000 individuals), some chemical analysis (PFOS, PFOA, PFHxS, PFDS, PFHxA, PFHpA, PFNA, PFDA, PFU(n)dA, PFDaA, PFTTrDA, PFTeDA) have already been conducted.

Norway

From Norway, the Norwegian Mother and Child Cohort Study (MoBa) was selected. This study is a prospective population-based pregnancy cohort study conducted by the Norwegian Institute of

⁸ Hutter HP, Wallner P, Hartl W, Uhl M, Lorbeer G, Gminski R, Mersch-Sundermann V, Kundi M. Higher blood concentrations of synthetic musks in women above fifty years than in younger women. *Int J Hyg Environ Health*. 2010 213(2):124-30. doi: 10.1016/j.ijheh.2009.12.002.

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Public Health⁹. The participants were recruited from all over Norway in 1999-2008, and 41 % of the invited women consented to participate. The cohort now includes some 114,500 children, 95,200 mothers and 75,200 fathers. MoBa includes information from The Medical Birth Registry of Norway, which comprises data on all births in Norway.¹⁰

For this theoretical study, a sub-study within MoBa, MoBa-ETox, will be described. MoBa-ETox is a part of the first phase of the Norwegian Human Environmental Biomonitoring Program and includes 2,999 pregnant women with available blood and urine samples from MoBa. Essential and toxic metals in blood (including Cd, Hg and Pb) have been analysed in addition to some vitamins, hormones and correction factors.

Sweden

From Sweden, the Northern Sweden Health and Disease Study was selected. This study includes several health examination surveys conducted within the adult population aged 25-74 years in Northern Sweden from 1986 onwards (the Northern Sweden MONICA Study and the Västerbotten Intervention Study). Questionnaire and medical data were collected at the baseline. For about 3,000 participants of these studies, lead and cadmium have been measured in whole blood or erythrocytes and for a proportion also mercury and some organic pollutants have been measured in blood or urine.

Also, a previously performed study will be described to illustrate the possibilities of registry linkage in Sweden. An HBM study on lead exposure in blood was conducted between 1978 and 2007 on 3176 primary school children in Southern Sweden. Each child's unique personal registration number was used to link to various national registers.

⁹ Magnus P, Birke C, Vejrup K, Haugan A, Alsaker E, Daltveit AK, et al. 2016. Cohort profile update: The norwegian mother and child cohort study (moba). *International journal of epidemiology* 45:382-388.

¹⁰ Irgens LM. 2000. The medical birth registry of norway. *Epidemiological research and surveillance throughout 30 years. Acta obstetrica et gynecologica Scandinavica* 79:435-439.